

TABLE 1.—NMR SIGNALS EXHIBITED BY THE C-3 PROTON OF SOME 3-ACETOXYFRIEDOOLEANANES

Name of the 3-acetates	Configuration of the C-3 proton	Nature of the NMR signal	Position of the signal (δ in ppm)
Putryl acetate(V) ²	α -equatorial	Triplet(1H)	4.90
3 α -Acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)ene(IV)	β -axial	Multiplet(1H)	4.62
Roxburgholone acetate(VI) ⁷	β -axial	Multiplet	4.60
3 α -Acetoxyfriedoolean-7-ene(VII) ⁹	β -axial	Multiplet	4.60
Friedelanyl acetate(VIII) ⁷	β -axial	Multiplet	4.62
Epi-friedelanyl acetate(IX) ¹⁰	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.87
3 β -Acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene(V)	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.90
3 β -Acetoxy friedoolean-7 β -ol(X) ⁶	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.90
3 β -Acetoxy friedoolean-7-ene(XI) ⁹	α -equatorial	Triplet	4.89

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. NMR spectra were taken at 270 MHz for solutions in deuteriochloroform with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. IR spectra were taken in Nujol.

Putrone (I)², natural putrol (III)² and the acetates (V)², (VI)⁷, (VII)⁹, (VIII)⁷, (IX)¹⁰, (X)⁶ and (XI)⁹ were prepared according to reported procedures.

Preparation of 3 α -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (IV): To a boiling solution of putrone(I; 400 mg) in amyl alcohol (15 ml) was added metallic sodium (600 mg) in small pieces and refluxing was continued until all the sodium dissolved. Excess amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation and the precipitated solid was worked up with ether. Chromatography over a column of silica gel followed by crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II; 200 mg), m.p. 229-231°. $\lambda_{\max}$ 3390 cm^{-1} (OH). (Found: C, 84.37; H, 11.76% and M^+ 412. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.40; H, 11.72% and M^+ 412).

The above compound (II; 100 mg) was acetylated with a mixture of acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) by heating over a steam-bath for 3 hrs. Usual work up afforded a crystalline solid, m.p. 208-212°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone afforded colorless needles of 3 α -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (IV; 40 mg), m.p. 215-217°. $\lambda_{\max}$ 1710, 1225 cm^{-1} (acetate). (Found: C, 81.85; H, 11.04%. M^+ 454. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.88; H, 11.08%. M^+ 454). The above acetate(IV) was also found to be different (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) from the acetate of natural putrol.

Preparation of 3 β -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (V): Putrone (I; 400 mg) was refluxed with a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride in purified¹¹ tetrahydrofuran for 6 hrs. Usual work up

afforded a solid, m.p. 190-194° which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded colorless crystals of 3 β -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (III; 200 mg), m.p. 198-200° and was found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with the natural putrol².

The above compound (III; 100 mg) was acetylated with a mixture of acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) by heating over a steam-bath for 3 hrs. Usual work up and chromatography over a column of silica gel afforded a solid, m.p. 212-216°, which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone furnished pure crystals of 3 β -acetoxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (V), m.p. 219-222°, which was found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with the acetate derived from natural putrol by reported² procedure.

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Bamford Stevens Reaction of 3 β -Acetoxy-cholest-5-en-7-one Tosylhydrazone

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FORMATION of substitution products on alkaline decomposition of tosylhydrazones of ketones¹ including saturated steroidal ketones² has been reported earlier. The present work describes similar

decomposition study of the tosylhydrazone II of an α , β -unsaturated steroidal ketone, namely 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (I). The product obtained after acetylation of reaction mixture is III. The structures of II and III have been established on the basis of spectral properties.

The reaction of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (I)⁸ in acetic acid with toluene-*p*-sulphonylhydrazide provides 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one tosylhydrazone (II), which analysed correctly for C₃₆H₅₄N₂O₄S. The ir and nmr spectral data given below are compatible with structure II.

IR : $\nu_{\max}$ 1735 ($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 1645 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}$),
1610 ($-\text{C}=\text{C}-$), 1240 cm^{-1} ($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$).

NMR : δ 7.32d (C₂'-H and C₆'-H ; J=9Hz), 7.2d (C₃'-H and C₅'-H ; J=9Hz), 5.7s, (C₆-H), 4.66br (C₃- α H, W $\frac{1}{2}$ =18Hz ; axial)⁴ and 2.02s

The tosylhydrazone II was subjected to sodium-ethylene glycol decomposition at 150°. The crude product thus obtained was acetylated with pyridine-acetic anhydride mixture and chromatographed over neutral alumina. Elution with light petroleum ether (4 : 1) furnished the compound III, m. p. 82° which analysed correctly for C₃₃H₅₄O₅. The ir and nmr spectral data recorded for the compound III supported the structure assigned.

IR : $\nu_{\max}$. 1745 ($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 1660 ($-\text{C}=\text{C}-$),
1245 cm^{-1} ($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$).

NMR : δ 5.6d (C₆-H ; J=2.8 Hz), 4.64br (C₃- α H ; W $\frac{1}{2}$ =18 Hz, axial), 4.22t (C₇- β H), 3.70q ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{OAc}$), 3.51q ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{OAc}$), 2.06s

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol with a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were run in CDCl₃ with A60 Varian instrument with TMS as the internal standard. TLC plates were coated with silica gel. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as spraying agent. Light petroleum refers to the fraction of b. p. 60-80°. NMR values are given in ppm (s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet, q=quartet, br=broad, w $\frac{1}{2}$ =half band width).

3 β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one tosylhydrazone (II) : The ketone I, m. p. 163° (2.5 g) was dissolved in warm glacial acetic acid (30 ml). The solution was cooled, the toluene-*p*-sulphonylhydrazide (2.5 g) was added with shaking and kept overnight at room temperature. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried. Recrystallization from methanol gave tosylhydrazone II (1.2 g), m. p. 158-159°. Found : C, 70.80 ; H, 8.83 ; N, 4.60. C₃₆H₅₄N₂O₄S requires : C, 70.82 ; H, 8.85 ; N, 4.58%.

Alkaline decomposition of II : 7 α -(2'-hydroxyethoxy) cholest 5-en-2',3-diacetate (III) : The tosylhydrazone (II) (1.0 g) was suspended in a solution prepared by dissolving sodium (2.5 g) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) and the mixture was heated on an oil bath for 2 hrs at 150°. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dil. HCl, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and finally with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil (1.3 g) which was treated with pyridine (2.5 ml) and acetic anhydride (1.5 ml). The reaction mixture was left overnight and then heated on water bath for 1 hr. It was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dil. HCl, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and finally with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil (0.73 g) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (15.0 g). Elution with light petroleum-ether (4 : 1) gave III as solid which was recrystallized from methanol (0.43 g), m. p. 81-83°. Found : C, 74.70 ; H, 10.11. C₃₃H₅₄O₅ requires : C, 74.72 ; H, 10.11%.

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Synthesis of Some 1-Methyl 4-Phenyl Piperidines

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MCELVAIN and Clemens¹ synthesised potent piperidine analgesics which contained alkyl and aryl substituent in the four positions. The most potent compound contained a meta-hydroxyl substituent in the aromatic ring. The analgetic activity disappeared when the hydroxyl group was introduced in the ortho or para position. Parcell² reported that some 4-(ortho-substituted phenyl)-1-hydroxyalkyl-piperidine showed hypotensive activity. To investigate pharmacological activity, a series of compounds of the type (I) has now been synthesised.

2-Alkyl-4,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde has been prepared from 3,4-dimethoxyalkyl-benzene by formylation with POCl₃ and dimethyl formamide. 2-Alkyl-4,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde has been treated with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of piperidine. The condensation product, a bis-acetoacetate, on hydrolysis gives 3-(2-alkyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid. The latter acid on heating with acetic anhydride has been converted to the corresponding glutaric anhydride. The anhydride reacts with methylamine to yield N-methyl imide. The imide on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride has yielded the desired product (I). Data of the compounds have been listed in the table.

Pharmacology : The compound (I : R = C₂H₅) in a dose of 2 mg/Kg produced a sharp and prolonged fall of blood pressure in anaesthetised cat. This fall could not be blocked by atropine or antihistaminic agent. At a very high dose (10 mg/Kg) the

TABLE

Name of the compound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis%						IR (cm ⁻¹)
			Requires			Found			
			O	H	N	O	H	N	
1. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₆	140	62.5	7.12	—	62.15	6.9	—	1721, 1734
2. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₆	135	63.3	7.33	—	63.0	7.12	—	1724, 1748
3. Ethyl-2,4-diacetyl-3-(2-n-propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutarate	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₆	152	64.0	7.55	—	63.5	7.05	—	1721, 1748
4. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₆	142	59.57	6.38	—	59.32	6.05	—	1695
5. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	151.5	60.81	6.75	—	60.25	6.55	—	1695
6. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₆	144	61.93	7.09	—	61.45	6.59	—	1695
7. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₅	95	63.63	6.06	—	63.12	5.68	—	1760
8. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₅	129.5	64.74	6.47	—	64.24	6.15	—	1760
9. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-glutaric anhydride	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅	135	65.75	6.84	—	65.53	6.41	—	1760
10. β-(2-Methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	158	64.98	6.85	5.05	64.54	6.35	5.1	1678
11. β-(2-Ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	112	65.97	7.21	4.81	65.59	7.03	4.33	1678
12. β-(2-n-Propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-N-methyl glutarimide	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	141	66.88	7.54	4.59	66.39	7.23	4.18	1678
13. 1-Methyl-4-(2-methyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	250	63.04	8.4	4.9	62.51	8.87	5.34	—
14. 1-Methyl-4-(2-ethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	240	64.1	8.01	4.67	64.27	8.52	4.95	—
15. 1-Methyl-4-(2-n-propyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-piperidine hydrochloride	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₂ NCl	178	65.07	8.93	4.46	65.90	9.30	4.77	—